

Cognitive-Behavioural Therapy vs. Psychoeducation: Comparative Effectiveness and Implications for Adolescent Treatment Development

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Abstract

Background: Emotional distress remains a significant contributor to mental health disorders globally, particularly among adolescents and in low-income rural areas with poor treatment rates, high prevalence, and a paucity of evidence-based treatment data.

Objective: This study evaluated the development and differential efficacies of brief cognitive-behaviour therapy (BCBT) and psychoeducation (PE) on emotional distress among adolescents in Oyo, South-West Nigeria.

Methodology: This study utilised a pre-test post-test control group experimental design. Seventy-two adolescents (mean age 13 years, $SD \pm 2$) were included in the sample. Participants were identified as having emotional distress, defined by a mean pre-test score of 31 points on the 21-item Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scales (DASS). The participants were randomly assigned by ballot into three groups—one control group and two experimental groups—with 24 participants per group.

Results: The results of the pairwise sample t-test showed that brief cognitive-behaviour therapy (BCBT) and psychoeducation (PE) treatments significantly lowered emotional distress [$t(20) = 6.9, p < 0.05$; $t(22) = 8.7, p < 0.05$] of experimental group participants compared to the control group [$t(19) = 0.1, p > 0.05$]. Independent samples t-test revealed that brief cognitive-behaviour therapy and psychoeducation at post-test and follow-up did not differ significantly in their effectiveness in reducing emotional distress [$t(42) = 1.6, p > 0.05$]; ($t(11) = 1.7, p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Both brief cognitive-behaviour therapy (BCBT) and psychoeducation (PE) were significantly effective in reducing emotional distress among adolescents, with the treatment gains being sustained at follow-up.

Unique Contribution: This study is among the first to establish and comparatively determine the differential sustainability of therapeutic efficacy between brief cognitive-behaviour therapy (BCBT) and psychoeducation (PE) in mitigating emotional distress among Nigerian adolescents.

Key Recommendation: It is strongly recommended that brief cognitive-behaviour therapy (BCBT) and psychoeducation (PE) be developed and formally integrated into adolescent school curricula. Further empirical research is warranted to support and refine this integration.

Keywords: Psychological treatments, mental health, adolescents, efficacy.

Introduction

Mental health issues, including psychological or emotional distress—commonly characterised by stress, anxiety, and co-occurring depressive symptoms—are significant contributing factors to global psychological disorders, particularly among adolescents (IHME, 2021; UNICEF, 2022). Among working-class adults, it is estimated globally that 12 billion workdays, amounting to \$1 trillion, are lost annually due to emotional distress, predominantly from symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress (WHO, 2022). High rates of emotional distress symptoms among adolescents have also been implicated in studies and linked with self-harm, suicide, risky sexual behaviour, substance use and abuse, poor grades, dropping out of school, and conflict/violence (Alinnor & Okefor, 2023; UNICEF, 2022; WHO, 2022).

It is estimated that over 41% of adolescents globally suffer from emotional distress such as depression and anxiety (UNICEF, 2022). Notably, higher rates of emotional distress appear to be more prevalent among low-income rural adolescents (Alinnor & Okefor, 2023; WHO, 2022), with poor treatment rates (Wang et al., 2023). Significantly, individuals residing in rural areas, especially in low-income countries, are negatively affected by numerous treatment barriers, including a lack of treatment awareness and accessibility, a shortage of trained experts, and a paucity of evidence-based psychological treatments, and effective alternative interventions, particularly among children and adolescents (UNICEF, 2022; WHO, 2022; Wang et al., 2023).

Researchers have suggested different treatment efficacies, such as medications alone, medication combined with psychotherapy, and cognitive behavioural therapy, including psychoeducation, as viable standalone treatments for emotional distress symptoms, depression, anxiety, and stress (Papini et al., 2023; Rathi et al., 2024). As an example, while the use of medication has been noted for its effectiveness in emotional distress symptom relief, it is often restricted among adolescents due to known side effects (UNICEF, 2023). Additionally, in reducing the severity of distress symptoms, combined treatment interventions, such as medication and psychotherapy, including cognitive-behavioural therapy, have also been found to be efficacious (Changklang & Ranteh, 2023; UNICEF, 2022). Also, cognitive-behaviour therapy administered in brief or standard, individual or group approach has been established effective at reducing emotional distress among adolescents by researchers (Are et al., 2022; Changklang & Ranteh, 2023; Egenti et al., 2021; Piro & Taha, 2023).

Changklang and Ranteh (2023) observed that emotional distress symptoms in a sample of adolescents aged 18 to 21 significantly improved after exposure to eight sessions of brief cognitive-behavioural therapy, as indicated by pre-test and post-test measures. Likewise, Piro and Taha (2023) found that the efficacy of brief cognitive-behaviour therapy, indicating that participants assigned to the treatment group experienced a significant decrease in elevated emotional distress symptoms at the post-treatment measurement following their exposure to brief cognitive-behaviour therapy, compared to a waitlisted control group. Similarly, Egenti et al. (2021) reported a significant reduction in psychological distress symptoms among undergraduate students who underwent 90 minutes of brief cognitive-behavioural therapy per session over six weeks. Studies have shown that exposing emotionally distressed adolescents to either brief or stand cognitive-behaviour therapy interventions significantly diminished emotional distress symptoms during post-treatment and follow-up periods (Abasilim & Obozekhai, 2024; Cully et al., 2020; Are et al., 2022; Duruji et al., 2021). Furthermore, utilisation of cognitive-behaviour theory in the treatment of emotional distress emphasises modification of the link between faulty thoughts, interpretation, or perception of an event, and not the occurrence of an event in causing emotional distress, depression, and or anxiety through the process known as psychoeducation, and cognitive restructuring (Cully et al., 2020).

Regrettably, the availability and accessibility to evidence-based treatment, cognitive-behaviour treatment, in low-income countries with a higher prevalence of distressed adolescents have been marred by a shortage of experts who can administer cognitive-behaviour therapy in either brief or standard sessions and the high cost of treatment (Are et al., 2022; Piro & Taha, 2023; Wang et al., 2023). In addition, the paucity of evidence-based alternative treatment data, the emigration of the few available professionals, and high treatment costs remain major challenges to evidence-based treatments in low-income rural areas (Abasilim & Obozekhai, 2024; Eze et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023).

The dearth of studies on awareness and efficacy of alternative treatments, such as psychoeducation, which involves providing information or knowledge on illness/condition, is suggested by researchers to be a viable cost-effective alternative to cognitive behaviour-therapy in the absence of trained cognitive-behaviour experts in low-income rural areas (Brooks et al., 2021; Jibunoh & Ani, 2022). Alternative viability of psychoeducation as a separate treatment intervention comes with ease of administration, lower demand for training skills, and affordability by both clinicians and non-clinicians in groups and individual settings (Odukoya et al., 2024; Papini et al., 2023; Rathi et al., 2024). Psychoeducation as a treatment emphasises the importance of providing knowledge on the cause of illness, symptoms, available treatments, and resources, following the Engel biopsychosocial model (Brooks et al., 2021). It is assumed that providing knowledge or education about psychological distress among adolescents will lead to help-seeking behaviour, which may result in a reduction in emotional distress (Olashore et al., 2023; Papini et al., 2023; Rathi et al., 2024).

As an example, Olashore et al. (2023) revealed a notable reduction in depressive symptoms following group participants' exposure to psychoeducation treatment conditions for five weeks and a twenty-four-week post-treatment follow-up. Similarly, Rathi et al. (2024) observed

significant improvement in the psychological well-being of control group participants exposed to depression literacy intervention. Additionally, Papini et al. (2023) revealed that psychoeducation remains a viable standalone treatment for emotional distress, as control group participants experienced notable symptom improvement after exposure to four and six weekly treatment sessions, respectively. However, Jibunoh and Ani (2022) observed that psychoeducation was not significantly effective in reducing anxiety among secondary school participants after three sessions. Typically, psychoeducation often faces challenges in terms of acceptance due to limited studies comparing the outcomes of cognitive-behavioural therapy and psychoeducation among adolescents with elevated emotional distress, especially in low-income rural areas (Eze et al., 2023). Given this gap, this study evaluated the development and differential efficacies of brief cognitive behaviour therapy and psychoeducation on emotional distress among adolescents.

To address this found gap, questions were raised on whether the two treatments, brief cognitive behaviour therapy, and psychoeducation, will be significantly effective in reducing emotional distress and if the treatment effectiveness differs in reducing emotional distress at post-test and follow-up. The study attempts to answer these questions by hypothesising that participants receiving either brief cognitive-behaviour therapy or psychoeducation will report significantly lower emotional distress symptoms compared to those in the control group and that there will be a significant difference in treatment effectiveness on emotional distress between participants exposed to brief cognitive-behaviour therapy and psychoeducation at post-treatment and follow-up.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A quasi-experimental study employing a pre-test and post-test control group design was conducted, consisting of two experimental groups and a control group. Participants were randomly selected from a pool of 465 individuals who responded to study-administered questionnaires from four secondary schools to obtain a baseline score (pre-test). An average (mean) score of 31 or above on emotional distress measured using the twenty-one-item depression, anxiety, and stress scale (DASS21) was adopted for the random selection of participants to either the experimental or control groups. Matched by schools, each group was assigned 24 participants by ballot. Four research assistants drew consecutively from a paper box containing wrapped papers with inscribed codes assigned to each respondent's questionnaire, which were placed into three brown envelopes labelled A, B, and C.

Study Setting

This study was conducted in Oyo-East Local Government Area (LGA) of Oyo Central Senatorial District, Oyo State, Southwest Nigeria. The school hall of one of these four secondary schools in Kosobo was purposively chosen for the treatment intervention due to its central location, road network, security, and accessibility to transportation, as well as the availability of an infirmary, ceiling fans, adequate chairs, tables, and a power supply.

Study Participants

A total of 72 participants with an emotional distress score of 31 or higher were selected and assigned into two experimental groups and a control group, with 24 participants per group, matched from the four selected secondary schools. Each group consisted of an equal number of 6 participants from each of the selected schools, selected consecutively by the four research assistants. Participants observed a mean age of 13 years (SD ± 2). Experimental group A had 24 participants, 12 male and 12 female. Likewise, experimental group B consisted of 24 participants, comprising 13 males and 11 females, while control group C consisted of 24 participants, comprising 11 males and 13 females. Experimental group A was exposed to brief cognitive-behavioural therapy, and experimental group B received psychoeducation. The control group received no treatment except for a one-off psychoeducation session at the end of the intervention.

Group Sample Size Determination

The study group sample size was determined by applying the statistical power analysis for the behavioural sciences through the a priori sample size calculator for the Student's T-test/One-way ANOVA to determine the minimum and maximum required number of participants in a group (as described by Cohen. The four factors described by Cohen were utilised as an effect size of 0.90, a statistical power level of 0.80, a probability level of 0.05, and a significance level of 0.05 (two-tailed). A maximum group size of 42 and a minimum of 21 participants per group (two-tailed) were determined. The minimum determined group sample size of 21, and an additional 3 participants were added by the researcher to ensure equal matching, possible group attrition, and a manageable class size. Study groups had 24 participants each.

Instruments

The short version of DASS21 was used to measure emotional distress in this study. The DASS is known for its reliability and validity among adolescents (Medvedev, 2023). Cronbach's alpha reliability with values of 0.81, 0.89, and 0.78 for the depressive, anxiety, and stress subscales, respectively, has been observed among Nigerian adolescents (Coker et al., 2018). Cronbach's reliability of 0.72, 0.64, and 0.66 was found in this study for depression, anxiety, and stress, respectively. Total inter-item correlation validity (r) ranges from 0.12 to 0.29. DASS low or high scores indicate lower or higher emotional distress among participants.

Procedure for Data Collection

Approval number NHREC/CU-HREC/11/04/2023 and CHREC/208/2023 was first obtained for this study from the Covenant University Health Research Ethics Committee. Informed permission letters were written to the schools, and consent to use the school was obtained from the schools' management on behalf of the participants' parents following a parent-teacher association meeting. The study questionnaire, consisting of DASS21, was administered to the students at their schools' halls during long recess to obtain a pre-test emotional distress score. Participants with a mean emotional distress score of 31 or higher were randomly assigned to the treatment and control groups. After exposing the treatment group participants to different treatment conditions—brief cognitive-behavioural therapy and psychoeducation—for six weeks, with 50-minute sessions each week, a post-test and follow-up score on emotional distress symptoms were obtained by re-administering the study questionnaire. Responding to the questionnaire lasted about 15 minutes.

The same venue, St. Francis Catholic College’s school hall, was used for the treatment sessions of both experimental groups, but on different days. Each of the experimental groups had a check-in list and check-out list of participants, prepared slides, and a projector utilised during sessions for the treatment content delivery.

Cognitive Behaviour Therapy Intervention

This treatment intervention consisted of six sessions, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1
Summary Content of Sessions and Purpose Weekly

Session’s	Activity	Purpose
Week Treatment Relationship	1: Introduction of treatment intervention. Members’ self-introduction. Communication of rules, tasks, and assignment expectations. Applause to expressions, and task completion were given. Male and female group volunteers shared refreshments at the end of each session.	To create a guided atmosphere of relational participation and confident self-expression.
Week Psychoeducation	2: Recognising feelings (emotions) through a pattern of thinking or interpretation given to what has happened in class, school, at home, or where we found ourselves. Participants expressed their thoughts on asking questions, answering questions, recalling what had happened before, the feelings experienced following the event, and how the event was viewed.	To enable participants to understand the connection and recognition of the occurrence of events, leading to feelings of distress, and what they did in response.
Week Changing Thought Patterns	3: How you perceive what has happened affects your feelings, either positively or negatively. Participants were asked to consider alternative views or interpretations of events they had experienced during the week. Alternative positive views were given to the prior negative interpretation of the event. Stepping out to communicate their alternative views was applauded by the group members.	To enable clarity in the knowledge that there is a link between one’s view of events and the distress symptoms experienced.
Week Changing Thought Patterns and observing you feel.	4: Recalling a past event, labelling how it was viewed negatively or positively. If negative, exploring the event and viewing it positively was the main activity for this session. With a prompting question such as How do you feel when you see it positively and then How do you feel when you view it negatively? The students answered positively, less sad, and relieved,	To enable change in negative patterned thinking to more positive resulting in less distress symptoms experience.

		compared to angry and ashamed, respectively, to the question. Four students stepped forward to share their experiences and were applauded.	
Week 5: Breathing it Out to Feel Relax		With a provision of explanation that the way we interpret events (negatively) affects how our body responds to what happened, such as difficulty breathing or a racing heartbeat.	To enable participants to have positive bodily responses and reduce negative thinking by controlled breathing patterns.
		The participants were exposed to the routine of deep breathing relaxation techniques,	
Week 6: Speaking self-positives		Thinking low and having a negative self-image during events exacerbates negative feelings (distress symptoms). To un-trap negatively, the participants were taught to see and voice positively at least one thing they did positively when the event happened, rather than listening to negative.	To enable participants to affirm self-positively when events occur.
		Participants were asked to mention or speak to themselves about the positives of the events.	

Psychoeducation Intervention

The six sessions of information giving were conveyed through slide projections, as outlined in Table 2.

Table 2
Summary of Delivered Psychoeducation Treatment Contents

Weekly Session's	Activity	Purpose
Week 1: Establishing Treatment Relationship	Group members' introduction. Overview of psychoeducation treatment and establishment of rules and expectations.	To elicit free participation within the group's agreed-upon rules.
Week 2: Mind distress and symptoms.	Assessment of prior knowledge of emotional distress and symptoms. Defining mind distress and symptoms examples include stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms. Introduction of causes of emotional distress.	To bring about an understanding of emotional distress and identification of symptoms.
Week 3: Biological factor causation of emotional distress and symptoms.	Inherited traits, one's genetic makeup, hormonal imbalance, brain structures, and pain were the causes mentioned. Headaches, stomach aches, and sleep issues were mentioned as symptoms.	To enable understanding of the biological causation of emotional distress and symptoms.

Week 4: Psychological factor causation of emotional distress and symptoms.	A negative pattern of seeing what happens. Thinking or feeling low or rating oneself poorly, or badly, often. Learned behaviour is one of the identified psychological causes. Difficulty concentrating, being withdrawn, and being angry were among the symptoms mentioned.	To enable understanding of the psychological causation of emotional distress and symptoms.
Week 5: Social factor causation of emotional distress and symptoms.	Being isolated by friends, parents' fights, arguments, divorce, and insults/abuse from teachers and peers is mentioned to cause distress symptoms. Loneliness, loss of appetite, fatigue, body weakness, avoiding classes, and poor grades were identified as symptoms one may experience as a result of social causation.	To enable understanding of the social causation of emotional distress and symptoms.
Week 6: Understanding what can be done	Sharing symptoms (feelings/thoughts) with school counsellors and class teachers, daily exercising, enrolling in therapy, asking family members (siblings, parents, etc.) for support, and visiting the clinic/hospital. Explain what people do that is not healthy.	To enable participants to understand and be aware of available help, treatments, healthy behaviours to adopt, and unhealthy ones.

Results

The results of the tested hypotheses for the study are presented in the tables below.

Table 3

Effectiveness of Treatments: Exposure of Experimental Group Participants Using Pairwise Sample T-test

Variable	Participants	Treatment	Measure	N	M	Std	Df	T	P
Emotional Distress	Group A	Cognitive Behaviour Therapy	Pre-test	21	51.2	15	20	6.9	<0.05
			Post-test	21	26.2	15.1			
	Group B	Psychoeducation	Pre-test	23	48.9	21.3	22	8.7	<0.05
			Post-test	23	19	13			
	Group C	No treatment	Pre-test	20	49.3	17	19	0.1	>0.05
			Post-test	20	48.3	30.6			

The results outlined in Table 3 indicate that participants in experimental groups A and B, who received brief cognitive-behavioural treatment and psychoeducation, respectively, experienced a significant reduction in emotional distress in line with the stated hypothesis of this study. By conducting a pairwise sample t-test, the experimental group A participants' post-test mean (26.2)

compared to their pre-test mean (51.2) revealed significantly lowered emotional distress symptoms after brief cognitive-behaviour treatment exposure. Similarly, a pairwise sample t-test conducted revealed that experimental group B participants' post-test mean (19) compared to their pre-test mean (48.9) revealed significantly lower emotional distress symptoms after exposure to psychoeducation. Also, participants in the control group C, who did not receive any treatment, maintained a high level of emotional distress, considering the mean pre-test (49.3) and post-test (48.3) scores.

The mean differences observed for the experimental groups showed that brief cognitive behaviour therapy and psychoeducation treatments were significantly effective in reducing the emotional distress symptoms of the group participants, with statistical values of ($t(20) = 6.9, p < 0.05$) and ($t(22) = 8.7, p < 0.05$), respectively. In comparison, the control group C showed no significant change in emotional distress symptoms, with ($t(19) = 0.1, p > 0.05$). Therefore, the first hypothesis was confirmed.

Table 4

T-test Comparing Means in Treatment Effectiveness of Brief Cognitive Behaviour Therapy and Psychoeducation at Post-test and Follow-up

Variable	Measure	Treatment	Participants	N	Mean	Std	Df	T	P
Emotional Distress	Post-test	CBT	Group A	21	26.2	15.1	42	1.6	>0.05
		Psycho-education	Group B	23	19	13			
	4weeks follow-up	CBT	Group A	12	29.8	16.9	11	1.7	>0.05
		Psycho-education	Group B	12	20	11.3			

Table 4, in line with the second study's stated hypothesis that there will be a significant difference in treatment effectiveness on emotional distress between participants exposed to brief cognitive-behaviour therapy and psychoeducation at post-treatment and follow-up, shows the means evaluations of post-treatment effect measures for participants assigned to group A, who received brief cognitive-behavioural therapy, and group B, who underwent psychoeducation. The independent sample t-test revealed no significant difference in the effectiveness of treatments, including brief cognitive behaviour therapy and psychoeducation, at post-treatment measures. The experimental group A, participants' mean (26.2) and experimental group B, participants' mean (19) scores after both groups were exposed to their respective treatments for six weeks, did not differ significantly ($t(42) = 1.6, p > 0.05$) at post-test. The result showed that group B participants had a lower mean score in the post-test.

Similarly, at four weeks follow-up, the treatment effects sustained between the compared means of group A (29.8), who received brief cognitive behaviour therapy, and group B mean (20), who received psychoeducation, did not differ significantly ($t(11) = 1.7, p > 0.05$). Therefore, the differences in the observed means revealed that both the treatment effect of brief cognitive behaviour treatment and psychoeducation at post-test and follow-up measures did not differ

statistically and significantly in efficacy at reducing emotional distress symptoms among the group participants (A, B), as shown in Table 4. Consequently, the second study hypothesis was not confirmed.

Discussion

This study assessed the development and comparative effectiveness of brief cognitive behavioural therapy and psychoeducation in reducing emotional distress symptoms among adolescents in low-income rural areas. It also aimed to determine if there was a significant difference in treatment outcomes between those who received brief cognitive behavioural therapy and those who underwent psychoeducation at the post-test and follow-up. The findings revealed that both treatments—when administered for an equal six-week period—resulted in a significant reduction in emotional distress symptoms compared to the control group, which received no treatment. The therapeutic components of the two treatments, as presented in sessions, led to a notable decrease in the emotional distress symptoms of participants, as shown in Tables 3 and 4.

The significant treatment effect of the study's brief cognitive behaviour therapy result appears to be consistent with a previous study showing that brief cognitive behavioural therapy significantly decreased depressive symptoms among adolescents (Are et al., 2022; Changklang & Ranteh, 2023; Piro & Taha, 2023). Are et al. (2022) found that emotionally distressed adolescents assigned to the treatment-intervention group showed a significant reduction after five sessions, with a post-treatment mean score of 4.60 compared to a baseline mean score of 17.05. Likewise, the found effectiveness of this study's brief cognitive behaviour therapy appears to be supported by the findings of Changklang and Ranteh (2023), which indicated significant improvement in depressive symptoms of adolescent group participants between the pre-test mean (6.84) and a mean score of post-test (3.48) after eight sessions of treatment exposure to cognitive behaviour therapy. Furthermore, Piro & Taha (2023) showed that exposure of experimental group participants to brief cognitive behaviour therapy was significant in lower distress symptoms, with a reported mean of (1.79) at post-treatment to (21.53) at pre-treatment, compared to control group participants, which gives credence to this study result.

Similarly, the components of psychoeducation treatment sessions in lowering emotional distress in this study were supported by Olashore et al. (2023) and Papini et al. (2023), who found that psychoeducation remains a viable alternative treatment, with significant symptom improvement observed after four and six weekly sessions, respectively. Olashore et al. (2023) found a significant reduction in the mean depressive symptoms of participants before (13.0) and 7 weeks after five weeks of psychoeducation exposure for group participants, which supports the findings in this study. Furthermore, psychoeducation treatment was observed to be significant and had a sustained effect on the emotional distress of experimental group participants during a two-week follow-up ($d=0.76$) when compared to the control group, who received no treatment, in a 2-week follow-up comparison with a waitlist control ($d = 0.57$) (Papini et al., 2023).

The compared treatment means outcomes of brief cognitive behavioural therapy and psychoeducation treatment conditions showed no significant difference in effectiveness between experimental groups A and B at both post-treatment and four-week follow-up exposure measures.

Therefore, psychoeducation treatment intervention components that provided essential knowledge on emotional distress, including its biological, psychological, and social causes, and guidance on managing and alleviating symptoms, significantly reduced distress symptoms, as brief cognitive behaviour therapy among the participants in this study.

Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that brief cognitive behavioural therapy and psychoeducation within treatment components developed were effective in mitigating high levels of emotional distress among adolescents. This is especially pertinent for low-income rural adolescents.

Consequently, both cognitive behavioural therapy and psychoeducation, as an alternative treatment, can be valuable in low-income settings, particularly in rural communities with limited access to mental health services. Policymakers may consider working with clinicians to integrate brief cognitive behavioural therapy sessions (approximately 50 minutes, similar to a lesson period) and psychoeducation into school curricula.

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